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Measuring the Work Values and work engagement of Employees: The Philippines Context

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Abstract. This study intended to determine the influence of work values on work engagement. To enrich the discussion on this particular topic, the literature was reviewed and theories were proposed on extrinsic and intrinsic work values. The study was intended for the employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region, Philippines. To gather the data, questionnaires were used and in interpreting the data, descriptive and inferential statistics were used such as weighted mean and Pearson r Correlation. Weighted mean was used to determine the level of work values such as extrinsic, intrinsic work values, and work engagement. While Pearson r was used to determine the correlation between work values and work engagement. The study found that employees of Divine Word Colleges view both values to be important and are considered high and their work engagement is also considered high. Finally, the study found that there is a correlation between work values and work engagement. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

Keywords. work values, extrinsic, intrinsic work values, work engagement

I. Introduction

Improving work performance and productivity does not have a simple solution and does not have an exact single solution. It is a complicated one because it involves many factors. It is the same case with work engagement because it deals with many dimensions. There is no single key that can be used to solve work engagement once and for all. Thus, the management needs to study the situation to determine the problems and identify the different factors that cause the problem. Find out which ones to be selected to be prioritized to improve work engagement. Bear in mind that financial rewards and other kinds of benefits are not the only factors that cause work performance or job satisfaction as pointed out by Korkki (2010) in the New York Times. The New York Times pointed out the result of a study by Kahneman and Deaton (2010) that money does nothing for happiness or emotional well-being or work engagement. The New York Times argued that people are leaving a high-paying job because of unsatisfying work, not because of lack of money (Korkki, 2010). This report suggests that the unsatisfying work is not associated with low paying job but the work itself. The work itself and the environment around it can be the cause of dissatisfaction. The report and such study just help us understand that

money does not make a worker satisfied and fulfilled but the work values which the workers hold important. Therefore, the above findings lead us to the theory of choosing a career and work values.

Many theorists contend that career and work values must be in alignment as pointed out by Castrillon (2010). According to her, choosing a career has something to do with one's work value preferences with what is most important to him or her. Take the example of work values presented by Pryor (1999, cited by Ho, 2006) such as self-development, security, independence, creativity, helping others, supervision, money, prestige, friendship, physical activity, detachment, lifestyle, and environment. These are the values that a person considers important when he/she is looking for a job. These values are motivating the person to work and to be realized. Therefore, the work becomes an expression of their work values. In that case, work must provide some room for the person to realize his/her personal work values such as self-development, security, independence, etc.

Job satisfaction is a product of harmony between the work and the work values of the person. A worker is happier when there is alignment between his/her work values and the work he/she chooses. Thus, it is recommended that a person should know his/her work values well so that he/she can choose a work that is aligned to his/her values (Castrillon, 2020, McKay, 2018). Studies on work values and job satisfaction had started earlier by Dawis and Lofquist (1984) and Super and Sverko (1995). Their study found that values are predictors of job satisfaction and also found that different job predicts satisfaction to different needs. These studies strengthen the idea of choosing a career that should match one's work values (Esquibel, et.al, 2019). It is an important step to achieve job satisfaction. Employees are leaving the work is because the work itself does not match their work values. It is the work values that determine the degree of importance of work to a person/employee (Krishnan, 2012).

There have been also studies related to work values and work performance and commitment. Those studies pointed out the role of work values in choosing one's career and in producing work output and job satisfaction. These studies argue that people choose a certain job in line with their work values and when the work values of the person are aligned with the work he/she chooses, they are not only causing the increase of performance, commitment but it also stimulates a job satisfaction (Somers & Birnbaum, 1998, Liao, et.al., 2012, Kuchinke, et.al., 2008). The correlation of work values and work outcomes is not only applicable to a particular place or country but is universal. For example, the study of Ueda and Ohzono (2012) in Japan on the influence of work values on job performance showed the same result that work values are an important predictor to work outcomes. A similar study was also conducted in China by Xiao and Froese (2008) on the influence of work values, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment among employees in China. The study showed that work values affect job satisfaction and organizational commitment. These findings are further strengthened by the study of Gesthuizen, et.al. (2019) on the across national work values and their effect on job satisfaction and performance. The study found that people's work values affect greatly their work performance and satisfaction.

Reading different studies, it is found that there have been many studies conducted concerning work values and job satisfaction, and work performance but there have been no studies about work values and work engagement. The three are different constructs. Work performance can only be measured through the tangible output that is pre-established by the organization by which the employees should meet (Levinson, 2003) but work engagement can be measured through three different measures such as the cognitive, affective, and conative dimension of the person toward the work (Kuok & Taormina, 2017). It is multidimensional constructs that include cognitive, affective, and conative dimensions. The current study is

pursuing this gap and would measure the extrinsic and intrinsic work values of employees and their work engagement which includes cognitive, affective, and conative dimensions.

The objective of the study is to help administrators to determine ways how to improve the work engagement of employees and identify areas of development particularly work value and work engagement.

The study is divided into five parts. The first part is about the introduction/rationale or the background of the study. The second part is the related literature review. This part explains the theories of the study supported by the previous literature that discusses similar topics with the current study. The third part is about the research methodology that discusses the research design, population, locale of the study, research instruments, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is the presentation of empirical data and analysis which presents the data gathered through questionnaires. The fifth part is the result and discussion that discuss the further result of the study.

II. Related Literature review

The purpose of the literature review is to find out the existing literature concerning the current topic. The review seeks the information or ideas related to the present study and also to help the researcher identifies the theories of the study and points out the gaps. Therefore, this part presents the theories based on that literature.

The Concept of Work Values

Before going into the discussion of work values, we need to understand the concept of values. Values are the personal principle that one holds to be important and it becomes the compass of his/her behavior (Rokeach, 1973). Researchers and psychologists argue that the behavior of a person often reflects his/her values and this is confirmed through researches. Researchers have found that values predict the behavior of a person (Meglino, Ravlin, & Adkins, 1989, Rokeach, 1973), and values become the source of motivation (Mankoff, 1974) and a guide for decision making (Brown & Associates, 2002). According to Brown and Associates (2002), work values are part of the individual value system. In other words, the individual value system becomes work values (Ronen, 1978). The values of the person become the values of his/her work and it is the value that guides him/her to choose the work (Kaygin & Culluce, 2013).

The concept of work values was brought into the academic discussion only in the early 70s by Zytowski (1970). Before his work, there were no clear definitions of work values. Work values were understood as interest, motivation, work needs, and work satisfaction. Though there was no clear definition of what work values are, however, series of discussions on work values were able to identify some dimensions of work values such as altruism, prestige, and autonomy (Zytowski, 1970). The discussion on these dimensions boiled down to identify the internal need and external need of the person which later they call intrinsic and extrinsic motivation (Zytowski, 1970). The extrinsic and intrinsic motivation provides understanding about the extrinsic and intrinsic value (Gesthuizen, 2019). These values become the internal and external aspiration of the person to pursue (Abun, et.al. 2019). These values are the reasons why a person pursues a different career. Some might be working to achieve economic security, prestige, recognition, achievement, self-realization, growth, self-development, creativity, autonomy, and other needs. To fulfill these needs, one has to look for work that can meet these needs and that can provide a venue where these needs can be realized (Basinska & Daderman, 2019). Therefore, work also does not only fulfill the physical need or external needs of the person but also satisfies the psychological need of the person such need for growth (Basisnka & Daderman,

2019), autonomy, competence, and relatedness need (Deci (Ryan, 2000). These needs represent what most important to the person to pursue and become the source of motivation that guides the behavior of the person (Schwartz, 1999).

From the concept of values, now we have an idea of what work value is. Work values are what the person believes is the most important to pursue (War, 2008, cited by Basinska & Daderman, 2020). Zytowski (1970, cited by Ho, 2006) argued that people's hold value to a work is called work values and this personal value influences the expectation of the person toward the work. It is what one believes important and desirable and it is really what matters to a person (Ho, 2006). Work values are often becoming a guiding principle when people decide to look for a job whether to work with the government or with the private sector or any kind of job. Studies have shown that the work values of a person become the compass to show him/her what job he/she is to take (Choi, 2016). Choi's study examined factors that affect the career choice of a person whether to choose to work with the public office or with the private companies or non-stock-non-profit organization. His study pointed out that people are more likely to choose to work with private businesses than to work with the government (Choi, 2016). Their choice to work with the private sector is influenced by their work values (Choi, 2016). This study was supported by the earlier study of Judge and Bretz (1992) that individuals are most likely choosing their first job following their work values. This is confirmed by Doyle (2019), that when a person looks for his/her new job, most likely he/she would choose a work that matches his/her values. The values help a person to choose what company or what position to take. Thus, a person needs to know his/her work values and align his/her values with the work that he/she is going to take up.

Studies have revealed the correlation between work values and job involvement, commitment, and satisfaction (Liao, et.al. 2011). The individual work values do not only support individual job performance but also causes the increase of job satisfaction and happiness as pointed out by the study of Knoob (2010, Nohari, 2013, Kalleberg, 1977, Ali & Panatik, 2015, Ravari, et.al., 2012) and it can also improve organizational commitment (Froese & Xiao, 2012). Caprino (2016) in his study pointed out that many are leaving their work or organization because of a misalignment of their work values and the values of the workplace and the work that they are given. The study of Van-Vianen and Dijk (2007) pointed out one of the reasons for job turnover, that high turnover is a result of misalignment of work values and the work given to the employees. This finding was supported by the latest study of Liu, et.al. (2020) which revealed that harmony between work values and the work given to the employees would improve job satisfaction and lower turnover intention.

Extrinsic Work Values

Before going into the discussion of extrinsic work values, we need to understand the concept of extrinsic value and other related concepts such as extrinsic motivation. Extrinsic value is somewhat derivative because it has a value only if it is attached to something else, it has no value on its own (Zimmerman, 2019). It has value because it helps or promotes something else good (Harold, 2005). In other words, it has value because of its instrumental value or utility and it is something external to the person or a thing (Zimmerman, 2019). Though the concept of external value provides us an understanding of what external value is but it does not provide us a better glimpse of the concept of external work values. To help us better understand the external work values, we need to understand the concept of external motivation because personal values become the source of motivation why a person pursues a certain goal or certain career (Ronen, 1978, Tranquillo &Stecker, 2016 cited by Cherry, 2020).

Extrinsic motivation is external motivation, a motivation that is originated from something external to the person. It is not originated from within the person. In a simple definition, it is a behavior that is motivated by external rewards (Cherry, 2020). People are doing a certain thing, not because they enjoy doing such a thing but because of certain things, they expect from doing such a thing. Concerning this, one may refer to the expectancy theory of Vroom (1964). Vroom in his expectancy theory argues that people are extending extra effort to improve their performance because they know that their performance will be recognized and rewarded. They must be convinced in the first place that their extra effort to the work would increase their performance and they have to believe that their improved performance will be recognized (Burkus, 2020). This theory has been used by the management to improve the work performance of employees through incentive programs and also to retain employees with the company (Rowley & Harry, 2011).

The concept of extrinsic work values is similar to the concept of extrinsic motivation. People who have extrinsic motivation perform better because they expect something (reward) out of their performance. It is similar to the idea of extrinsic work values. Extrinsic work values are what one gets out of the work he/she performs. One expects to increase in his/her pay when his/her performance is getting better. His main objective is money or economic returns. The desired ends serve as a source of motivation of why a person pursues a certain job/work and why a person exerts extra effort in his/her work. For a certain person, money is what he/she believes to be a more important value for him/her to be achieved and this leads a person to choose a specific behavior/action to achieve such desired end (Schwartz, 1992). As Gesthuizen, et.al. (2019, p.2) say that “it serves as a general motivation to work and what kind of work we are looking for”.

The motivation of each person is different and it serves as the reason why different person pursues a different kind of job. Some might be looking for a lucrative job that offers economic benefits even though the other aspect of the work environment may not be pleasant to him/her and others may be looking for a job that they can enjoy, not for external reasons other than the work itself (Kaasa, 2011). Unfortunately, there have been no commonly accepted variables or dimensions on how to measure the extrinsic work values. The different nature of motivation of each leads to researchers' confusion to offer common dimensions about extrinsic work values (Cemalcilar, 2018). Miller (1974) offers nine dimensions of work values such as independence, prestige, economic returns, security, surroundings, supervisory relations, associates, way of life, and variety. While Kelleberg (1977) identified five dimensions related to work values such as convenience, financial, relationship with co-workers, the opportunities the job provides for a career, and resource adequacy. Lofquist and Dawis (1978) offered 12 dimensions of external work values such as ability utilization, achievement, activities, compensation, independence, security, variety, work conditions, advancement, authority, recognition, status, co-worker, moral values, social services, company policies, supervision of human relation, creativity, responsibility, and supervision of technical skills. Jurgensen (1978) classified 10 dimensions of work values such as security, hours, pay, benefits, working conditions, advancement, types of work, company, co-workers, and supervisor.

Studies have also shown that external work values can affect job performance, job involvement job satisfaction, and Career satisfaction of employees as pointed by the study of Merriman (2016), Teng (2010) and Kuchinke, et.al. (2008). These findings were built on the study of Hegney, et.al. (2006) that intrinsic and extrinsic work values impact job satisfaction and the intention to leave employment. These findings were further strengthened by the study of Ali and Panatik (2013) as they pointed out the effect of work values and work-related attitude. Such a study indicated that the work values of employees influence the work-attitude of

employees. Though the study of Ueda and Ohzono (2012) supports such findings, that there is a relationship between work values and work outcomes, however, the effect or the influence is different between job categories.

Intrinsic Work Values

To understand better the concept of intrinsic work values, let us go back again to the concept of value. Value can be defined in many different ways and therefore, we cannot pick up every definition to guide our discussion. Related to the topic at hand, Merriam Webster Dictionary defines value as a “relative worth, utility or importance”. While Macmillan Dictionary defines value as "principles or beliefs, importance or usefulness or amount something is worth". From these definitions, we can formulate one definition of value related to the current topic. Value is about one's belief of what is most important or valuable or useful to him/her. This definition is similar to the definition offered by Ho (2006, p. 17, as cited from Rokeach, 1973) that value is “ a principle or standard held in high esteem by an individual, and is related to all aspects of one's personal and work-life". These definitions are related to the concept of Schwartz (1992, 1994, p.20) about values. For him, values are about a belief of a person about what is important for him/her which becomes the basis of his/her priorities.

The definition presented above is related to the concept of extrinsic value because something has value because of its usefulness or its importance for a human being. In this case, value is seen as an instrument which means that something has value if it is useful and important for human welfare. Blackburn (2008) in the Oxford Dictionary of Philosophy (2008) defines instrumental values “as a means to something else”. Something has no value in itself if it is not important to achieve the other ends. While intrinsic values mean something has a value "in itself, for its own sake and in its own right" (Zimmerman, 2019) even though it is not useful and important for human welfare. Despite its usefulness for other ends, it has a value on its own and therefore it demands to be treated as such despite its importance for human beings' welfare because it is considered ends in itself (de Genaro, 2012). Intrinsic value as opposed to the extrinsic value and from here we understand the concept of intrinsic work value.

To capture a better understanding of intrinsic work values may not be enough just to understand the concept of intrinsic value itself but we need to explain the concept of intrinsic motivation because they are related. Intrinsic motivation is driven intrinsically, not because of reward or punishment. A person pursues an activity, not because of external rewards such as money or prestige but because he/she enjoys doing the activity or doing the work. The purpose of someone doing the job is to learn, to grow, and to realize his/her potentials (Cherry, 2019). Thus, intrinsic work values are similar to the intrinsic motivation concept because work values are the general motivation to work (Gesthuizen, et.al.2019). It is the motivation to work not for something external to the person but something to realize the full potential of the person. In this case, work is not an instrument to achieve the desired end such as money or prestige but work is actually to make himself/herself better, to make him/her grow in terms of knowledge and skills. It has something to do with the work itself and the intrinsic motivation of the person. The work realizes his/her potentials and thus makes him happy (Mckay, 2018). This is classified by Wu, et.al. (1996) as terminal values such as self-growth, self-realization, and self-esteem. People are working not only for money or prestige but to learn new knowledge and to make him/her grow (Wu, et.al. 1996). However, this kind of motivation can only be fulfilled when the work environment provides them a venue where they can apply their talent, creativity, and autonomy (Wu, et.al., 1996). Again, unfortunately, there have been no common dimensions about intrinsic work values presented by different researchers and as a result, the different researcher has offered different intrinsic work values dimensions such as Ginzberg, et.al. (1951)

identified seven dimensions of intrinsic work values such as interesting, being useful to society, challenging, achievement, independence, creativity, and the inside satisfaction of employees. Wollack, et.al. (1971) singled out three dimensions of intrinsic work values which include pride in work, job involvement, and activity preference and Miller (1974) presented seven intrinsic work values such as altruism, aesthetic, creativity, intellectual stimulation, achievement, and management.

Studies have offered evidence that there is a correlation between intrinsic work values and job satisfaction, performance, and involvement such as the study of Hegney, et.al. (2006), Knoob (2010), Kalleberg (1977). These findings are also supported by the study of Vansteenkiste and De Witte (2002) that intrinsic work values predict job vitality, job satisfaction, and commitment and negatively related to work burn-out. This finding is similar to the study of Putti, et.al. (1989) that intrinsic work values are more closely related to organizational commitment. In a summary of literature reviews on the correlation between work values and job satisfaction and commitment, Ali (2013) concluded that intrinsic work values and extrinsic work values are all predicting factors.

Work Engagement

The organizational performance is not isolated from work engagement. The issue of work engagement is important for management to know so that they know what to do to improve the work engagement of their employees. Failing to pay attention to the issue means failing to achieve the organizational goals because the goals can only be achieved through employees who perform and engage in their work (Tricore, 2016). However, the issue of work engagement is not just simple as job performance because job performance can be measured through tangible output based on the pre-set standards (Lebednik, 2017) but performance is only one aspect of work engagement. Work engagement is defined as "a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption" (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004, cited by Listau, et.al. 2017). The definition represents the mental, emotional, and physical aspects of the work. In other words, work engagement involves energy, mental, feeling of enthusiasm, and engrossment in one's work (Listau, et.al. 2017). Thus measuring work engagement is a multidimensional construct (Bakker, et.al. 2010, Kahn, 1990) because it has three dimensions namely cognitive, affective, and conative dimensions. Concerning the cognitive dimension, it has been argued that when people have an idea about the work, they become more aware of their work and would be more focused on their work and would have positive ideas about their work (Kuok & Taormina, 2017). The affective dimension of the work involves the feeling of the person toward the work. Those who are engaged in their work are signs that they are happy and excited with their work and having such kind of feeling would help them to accomplish their work (Kuok & Taormina, 2017). While conative dimensions explain the physical involvement of the person in the work. Having a good idea and positive feeling toward the job is always translating into behavior or action. It is only through action, the task can be accomplished. People exert effort and energy to accomplish their work is a sign of engagement. However, physical engagement is not only measured through the amount of energy spent on the work but is also measured through its intensity or frequency (Kuok & Taormina, 2017). This can explain the reason why some people are always in their work and never abandoned their duties and responsibilities.

Many studies have shown that work engagement correlates to organizational performance. The study of Patro (2013) found that employees' engagement results in organizational productivity, customer satisfaction, and the financial success of the company. But the study also pointed out that such kind of engagement is the product of a satisfied worker.

Employees who are satisfied consequently engaging their work which leads to organizational performance (Ali, et.al. 2018). Similar findings were also presented by the study of Singh (2019), Shrestha (2019), Dajani (2015), and Kazimoto (2016). Their study revealed that work engagement, organizational commitment are predictors of organizational performance. They recommended that giving attention to the factors that improve work engagement is one of the major duties of the management.

Source: Gesthuizen, et.al. (2019) and Kuok and Taormina (2017)

Figure1: The conceptual framework reflects the independent and dependent variables. Independent and dependent variables are used in experimental research. In the experimental research, the experimenter can only control or change the independent variables and the changes in the independent variables can cause a change in the dependent variables (McLeod, 2019). The framework reflects the correlation between independent and dependent variables. It shows that changes in the extrinsic and intrinsic variables can cause a change in the work engagement of employees.

Statement of the Problems

The study intends to investigate the influence of work values particularly extrinsic and extrinsic work values on the work engagement of employees of the Catholic Colleges in the Ilocos Region. It specifically seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the work values of employees in terms of
 - a. Extrinsic Work Values
 - b. Intrinsic Work Values
2. What is the work engagement of employees in terms of
 - a. Cognitive work engagement
 - b. Affective work engagement
 - c. Conative work engagement?
3. Is there a relationship between extrinsic and intrinsic work values or employees and their work engagement?

Assumption

The study assumes that work values such as extrinsic and intrinsic work values of employees affect their work engagement and these variables can be measured. It is also assumed that the questionnaires are valid and the response is objective.

Hypothesis

The study of Ho (2006) on the correlation between work values and job involvement and organizational commitment found that there is a correlation between work values and job involvement and organizational commitment. Building on his work, the current study hypothesizes that there is a correlation between work values such as extrinsic and intrinsic work values and work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region.

Scope and Delimitation of the study

The study covers the Catholic Colleges in the Ilocos region and it delimits its investigation on the work values of employees only to their extrinsic and intrinsic work values (Gesthuizen, 2019, Wu, et.al. 1996) and their work engagement in terms of cognitive, affective and conative work engagement. The limitation of the study is the coverage. It does not reflect the whole picture of Divine Word Colleges in Region I and in the Philippines.

III. Research Methodology

The research methodology is the process of how the study was conducted. Quality and scientific research is following the rules of the investigation. Wilkinson, (2000), and Leedy, (1974) argued that scientific research follows a specific procedure or technique to identify, select, process, and analyze information about a topic. In line with such a concept, the current study follows the rule of the scientific investigation, and therefore the current study used a certain research design, data gathering instruments method, the population, the locale of the study, the data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design of the study

The study used a descriptive assessment and correlational research design to determine the level of the extrinsic and intrinsic work values of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region, and its effect on work engagement. Ariola (2006) contended that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. In short, it answers the question of what, when, how, where, and not why question (McCombes, 2020).

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Catholic Colleges in the Ilocos Region.

Population

The respondents of the study are the employees of these colleges. Since the number of employees is limited, therefore, the total enumeration sampling was used and thus 163 faculty and employees were taken as respondents of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adapted the list of extrinsic work values of Miller (1974), Kelleberg (1977) and Lofquist and Dawis (1978) in measuring the extrinsic work values and the list of Wu, et.al. (1996), and Ginzberg, et.al. (1951) in measuring the intrinsic work values. While measuring

the work engagement, the Work Engagement Inventory with three 6-item subscales of Kuok and Taormina (2017) was used.

Data Gathering Procedures

To maintain the integrity of the investigation and to ensure that the data are gathered through the right process, thus, before the researcher distributes the questionnaires, letters were sent to the Presidents of the colleges to request them to allow the researcher to float his questionnaires in their respective institutions. In the process of collecting the data, the researcher requests employees' representatives to retrieve the data from different individual employees before they are submitted to the researcher.

Ethical Procedures

The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the content of the paper if it does not violate ethical standards and if it does not cause harm to human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, a descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of extrinsic and intrinsic work values and the Pearson r or Product Moment Correlation was used to measure the correlation between extrinsic, intrinsic work values and the work engagement of employees.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>Most Important/ Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Important/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat Important/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Not Important/Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Least Important/Very Low/Very High</i>

IV. Empirical Data and Analysis

The following are data gathered through questionnaires and have been statistically computed. The data are presented according to the arrangement of the statement of the problems of the study.

Problem 1: 1. What are the work values of employees in terms of

a. Extrinsic Work Values

b? Intrinsic Work Values

Table 1. The Work Values of Employees in terms of Extrinsic Work Values

Indicators	Mean	DR
1. Economic returns (salary)	3.83	I
2. Social prestige	3.66	I
3. Management recognition	3.66	I
4. Security	3.91	I
5. Human relations (between employer-employees)	3.83	I
6. Working condition	3.85	I
7. Company policies	3.81	I
8. Resource adequacy	3.75	I
9. Benefits	3.88	I

10. Clean surroundings	3.94	I
Composite Mean	3.81	I

Source: Miller (1974), Kelleberg (1977) and Lofquist and Dawis (1978)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Most Important</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Important</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat Important</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Not Important</i>	<i>Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Least Important</i>	<i>Very Low</i>

As gleaned from the data presented on the table, it shows that as a whole, the work values of employees in terms of extrinsic work values obtained a composite mean of 3.81 which is described as "Important/High". In other words, the extrinsic work values of employees are considered not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. This evaluation indicates that extrinsic work values are still seen as an important driver of employees' work behavior and work motivation. Even when the items are taken singly, they all show the same level of output which fall within the same description as "important" such as "economic returns (salary) (3.83), social prestige (3.66), management recognition (3.66), security (3.91), human relations (3.83), working condition (3.85), company policies (3.81), resource adequacy (3.75), benefits (3.88) and clean surroundings" (3.94).

Table 2. The Work Values of Employees in terms of Intrinsic Work Values

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>DR</i>
1. Individual growth	3.99	I
2. Learn new knowledge, new skills	4.05	I
3. Life meaning	4.06	I
4. Creativity	4.01	I
5. Autonomy,	3.88	I
6. Being useful to society	4.02	I
7. Pride in work	3.93	I
8. Intellectual stimulation	4.01	I
9. Achievement	3.99	I
10. Altruism (helping other people)	4.04	I
Composite Mean	4.00	I

Source: Wu, et.al. (1996), and Ginsberg, et.al. (1951)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Most Important/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Important/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat Important/moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Not Important/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Least Important/Very Low</i>

Following the extrinsic work, values are the intrinsic work values. As shown on the table, the data portray that as a whole, the work values of employees in terms of intrinsic work values gained a composite mean of 4.00 which is interpreted as "important/high". The evaluation points out that the intrinsic work values of employees are not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. This result implies that besides extrinsic motivation, intrinsic motivation is still considered an important source of motivation for employees' work behavior. Even if the items are taken separately, they all are evaluated within the same level of

weighted mean with the interpretation of “important/high” such as: “individual growth (3.99), learn new knowledge/skills (4.05), life meaning (4.06), creativity (4.01), autonomy (3.88), being useful to society (4.02), pride in work (3.93), intellectual stimulation (4.01), achievement (3.99) and altruism (helping others) (4.04).

Table 3. Summary of Work Values of Employees

ITEMS	Mean	DR
1. The Work Values of Employees in terms of Extrinsic Work Values	3.81	I
2. The Work Values of Employees in terms of Intrinsic Work Values.	4.00	I
Overall Mean	3.91	I

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Most Important/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Important/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Not Important/Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Least Important/Very Low/Very High</i>

The summary table demonstrates that overall, the work values of employees gained an overall mean rating of 3.91 which is described as "important/high". In other words, the work values of employees, both, extrinsic and intrinsic work values are high. This result suggests that extrinsic and intrinsic work values of employees are an important source of motivation of work behavior and at the same time both are always going together as a source of motivation of their work behavior. Neglect one of these motivations may affect the other one.

Problem2: What is the work engagement of employees in terms of

- a. *Cognitive work engagement*
- b. *Affective work engagement*
- c. *Conative Work Engagement*

Table 4. Work Engagement of Employees in terms of Cognitive Work Engagement

Indicators	Mean	DR
1. My mind is often full of ideas about my work.	3.87	A
2. Wherever I am, things happen that often remind me of my work.	3.80	A
3. My mind is fully engaged with my work.	3.91	A
4. I rarely think about a time when I am working.	3.82	A
5. My thoughts are fully focused when thinking about my work.	3.84	A
6. I give a lot of mental attention to my work.	3.85	A
Composite Mean	3.85	A

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

As displayed on the table, the data illustrates that as a whole, the work engagement of employees in terms of cognitive work engagement gained a composite mean of 3.85 which is described as "agree or high". This result indicates that the cognitive work engagement of employees is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. This evaluation recommends that employees have a high idea about their work and engage intellectually in their work. Even when the items are taken singly, they all are rated within the same level of mean interpretation as "agree/high" such as "their mind is full ideas about the work (3.87), wherever they are, they are thinking of their work (3.80), their mind is fully engaged in the work (.3.91), they rarely think about the time when they are in the work (3.82), their thoughts are fully focused when thinking about their work (3.84), and they give a lot of mental attention to their work" (3.85).

Table 5. Work Engagement of Employees in terms of Emotional Work Engagement

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>DR</i>
1. I feel very delighted about what I am doing whenever I am working.	3.85	A
2. I am very eager to do my work.	3.89	A
3. I feel very happy when I am carrying out my responsibilities at work.	3.94	A
4. I feel very good about the work that I do.	3.96	A
5. I feel strong enthusiasm for my work.	3.88	A
6. I feel a sense of gratification with my work performance.	3.87	A
Composite Mean	3.90	A

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

Even in terms of emotional or affective work engagement, the result indicates the same. As seen on the table, the data manifest that as a whole, work engagement of employees in terms of emotional work engagement obtained a composite mean of 3.90 which is described as "agree or high". These composite means indicate that emotional work engagement of employees is considered not very high but high and it is also not moderate, low, or very low. This evaluation suggests that employees of the college are highly engaged in their work emotionally. Even when the items are taken separately, they all are rated within the same level of mean with the same interpretation as "agree/high" such as, "feeling very delighted about what they are doing whenever they are working (3.85), are very eager to do their work (3.89), very happy when they are carrying out their responsibilities at work (3.94), feeling very good about the work that they do (3.96), feeling strong enthusiasm for the work (3.88), and feeling a sense of gratification with the work performance" (3.87).

Table 6. Work Engagement of Employees in terms of Physical Work Engagement

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>DR</i>
1. No matter how much I work, I have a high level of energy.	3.85	A
2. I have a great deal of stamina for my work.	3.89	A
3. I always have a lot of energy for my work.	3.94	A
4. I am often physically driven by my work.	3.96	A

5. I am frequently energized by my work.	3.88	A
6. I find my work to be physically invigorating.	3.87	A
Composite Mean	3.90	A

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

As indicated by the data, it reveals that as a whole, the work engagement of employees in terms of physical (conative) work engagement obtained a composite mean rating of 3.90 which is also interpreted as "agree or high". This evaluation manifests that the physical work engagement of employees is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. The composite mean suggests that employees agree that they are highly engaged in their work physically. Even when the items are taken separately, they all fall within the same level mean rating with the same interpretation as agree/high" such as "having a high level of energy (3.85), having a great deal of stamina (3.89), having a lot of energy (3.94), are physically driven by the work (3.96), are energized by the work (3.88) and finding the work to be physically invigorating" (3.87).

Table 7. Summary of Work Engagement of Employees

ITEMS	Mean	DR
1. Cognitive Work Engagement	3.85	A
2. Emotional Work Engagement	3.90	A
3. Physical Work Engagement	3.90	A
Overall Mean	3.88	A

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

The summary table indicates that the overall mean rating of work engagement of employees is 3.88 which is described as "agree or high". The result implies that the work engagement of employees is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. This evaluation points out that employees agree that they are highly engaged in their work cognitively, effectively, and physically. In other words, their engagement highly involves the whole self.

Problem3: Is there a relationship between extrinsic and intrinsic work values or employees and their work engagement?

Table 11. Relationship between Extrinsic and Intrinsic Work Values of Employees and their Work Engagement.

	Cognitive Work Engagement	Emotional Work Engagement	Physical Work Engagement
Pearson Correlation	.244**	.186*	.188*

Extrinsic Work Values	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.017	.016
	N	163	163	163
Intrinsic Work Values	Pearson Correlation	.445**	.440**	.390**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	163	163	163

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

As reflected on the Pearson r correlation table, it shows that there is a significant correlation at 0.01 level (2-tailed) and 0.05 level (2-tailed) between work values particularly extrinsic and intrinsic work values and work engagement of employees. This result suggests that both extrinsic and intrinsic work values are a predictor of employees' performance. Thus, any changes related to extrinsic and intrinsic work values will necessarily affect the performance or work engagement of employees particularly cognitive, affective, and physical work engagement.

V. Result and Discussion.

Work values are influenced by a particular context or culture and therefore work values may vary, not only across countries but even within a country, institutions, and even among individuals (Hofstede, 1980, Nystrom, 2020, Pryce, 2014). It has been argued that demographics, nationality, organizations, and occupation influence the work values of employees (Pryce, 2014). Based on the finding of the study, it shows that in the context of the Divine Word Colleges, both work values are strong predictors of employee performance. This is supported by the finding of the study that both values are rated within the same level mean rating which implies that both values cannot be neglected in managing work performance or work engagement of employees. The current finding suggests that management should give balanced attention to both work values. In the first place, the management should not prioritize tangible rewards in motivating employees and neglect the intangible rewards. Overemphasizing one work value and neglecting the other one may cause dissatisfaction. Finding the equivalence between the two work values is management's responsibility (Gesthuizen, et.al.2019). Studies have shown that neglecting intrinsic and extrinsic work values is one of the causes of job dissatisfaction and high turnover of employment (Hegney & Plank, 2006).

Besides finding the equivalence, another challenge for the management is to tailor the motivation strategies according to the motivation of individual employees. It cannot be denied that each employee is not only motivated to work by organizational values but it is also motivated to work by his/her values (All Answers Ltd., 2018, Ez-Eldin, et.al.2018, Thomas, 2013). Though employees must indeed align their work values with the values of the organization (Robino, 2007, Boreham, 2016), however, personal values still play important role in employees' work motivation and misalignment always happen and this is the main reason for low work performance (Hutter, 2017). The reality post a particular challenge not only on the part of the management to align corporate values with the employees' values and on the part of employees to align their values with the corporate values which may not be easy to be done.

Another relevant challenge for management and employees is also about how the management can integrate the extrinsic work values into the values of employees which can be identified with the employees. On the part of employees, to integrate their external values into their values. In short, the challenge is how to integrate and internalize those external values into their values (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Instead of seeing it as something external to them but it is something that belongs to them. Why the integration and internalization are important? When

the employees can integrate and internalize those external values into themselves, then they will not see those values as something external to them and see them as a burden to them or as pressure on them. Psychologist contends that brains do not work well under pressure (Schicker, 2020) and unhappiness can be the result of it.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, the study concludes that the employees of Divine Word Colleges are equally motivated by extrinsic and intrinsic work values. Employees considered both values important and it is considered high on both values. It is also found that both values are strong predictors to work engagement. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

The current finding contributes to the discussion on the work values. The result of the study post a particular challenge for the management and employees on how to harmonize corporate and individual values. Failing to harmonize employees' values and corporate values may cause underperformance. Employees' failure to harmonize their values to the corporate values may cause dissatisfaction and resignation.

References

- [1] Abun, D., Magallanes, T., Agoot, F., & Barroga, J.R. (2019). Extrinsic and Intrinsic Aspirations of students of Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region, Philippines, and their Academic performance. *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, 4(2).
- [2] Ali, N.A.M. & Panatik, S.A. (2015). Work Values and Job Satisfaction among Academicians in Public and Private University. *Jurnal Kemanusiaan*, 24 (2).
- [3] Ali, M., Masadeh, R., Khalaf, R.K.A., & Obeidat, B. (2018). The Effect of Employee Engagement on Organizational Performance via the Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction: The Case of IT Employees in Jordanian Banking Sector. *Modern Applied Science*, 12(6):17
- [4] Ali, N.A.M. & Panatik, S.A. The Relationships between Work Values and Work-Related Attitude: The Role of Social Support as a Moderator. *Journal of Social and Development Sciences*, 4(8), 369-375.
- [5] All Answers Ltd. (2018). Personal and Workplace Values: The Effect on Job Performance and Commitment. Retrieved from [https://ukdiss.com/examples/workplace-values-effect-job-performance.php?vref=. 1](https://ukdiss.com/examples/workplace-values-effect-job-performance.php?vref=.)
- [6] Bakker, A.B., Albrecht, S., & Leiter, M.P. (2010). Key questions regarding work engagement. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 20 (1), 74 — 88. DOI: 10.1080/1359432X.2010.546711
- [7] Blackburn, S. (2008). Instrumental Value. *The Oxford Dictionary of Philosophy*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [8] Boreham, I.D. (2016). Matching Personal Values to Organizational values-What the Theory Says. Retrieved from <https://www.linkedin.com>
- [9] Brown, D. & Associates (2002). *Career Choice and Development* (4th Ed.). New York: Jossey-Bass
- [10] Burkus, D. (2020). Extrinsic Vs. Intrinsic Motivation. *Psychology Today*. Retrieved from <https://www.psychologytoday.com>
- [11] Caprino, K. (2016). If Your Values Clash with how you are working, You'll suffer: Here is how to fix that. *Forbes*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com>

- [12] Castrillon, C. (2020). Why Your Work Values are Essential to Career Satisfaction. Forbes. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com>
- [13] Cemalcilar, Z., Secinti, E., & Sumer, N., (2018). Intergenerational transmission of work values: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 47 (8): 1559–79.
- [14] Cherry, K. (2020). The difference between Extrinsic and Intrinsic Motivation. Very Well Mind. Retrieved from <https://www.verywellmind.com>
- [15] Cherry, K. (2019). Intrinsic Motivation. Very Well Mind. Retrieved from <https://www.verywellmind.com>.
- [16] Choi, Y. (2016). Work Values, Job Characteristics, and Career Choice Decisions: Evidence from Longitudinal Data. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 47(7)
- [17] Dajani, M.A. (2015). The Impact of Employee Engagement on Job Performance and Organisational Commitment in the Egyptian Banking Sector. *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 3 (5), 138-147.
- [18] Dawis, R. V. & Lofquist, L. H. (1984). *A Psychological Theory of Work Adjustment: An Individual-Differences Model and Its Application*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- [19] Deci, E. L. & Ryan, R.M. (2000). "Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations: Classic Definitions and New Directions". *Contemporary Educational Psychology*. 25(1): 54 67. CiteSeerX 10.1.1.318.808. <https://doi.org/10.1006/ceps.1999.1020>
- [20] De Genaro, I. (2012). *Value: Sources and Readings on a Key Concept of the Globalized World*: Netherlands: Brill
- [21] Doyle, A. (2019). How to Assess Your Career Values. Balance Careers. Retrieved from <https://www.thebalancecareers.com>
- [22] Ez-Eldin, K.S., Alasser, N., Bahie, S., & Mors, M. (2018). The Effect of Employees' Personal Values on Achieving Organizational Strategic Goals. MBA Thesis: Fayoum University. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net>. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17925.09445>
- [23] Esquibel, J.A., Nicholson, B., & Murdock, J. (2019). Understanding the Impact of career Values on Career satisfaction: Utilizing Card Sorts in Career Counseling. *Career Planning and Adult Development Journal*, 35(1).
- [24] Froese, F.J. & Xiao, S.S. (2012). Work values, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in China. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management* 23(10):2144-2162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2011.610342>
- [25] Gesthuizen, M., Kovarek, D. & Rapp, C. (2019). Extrinsic and Intrinsic Work Values: Findings on Equivalence in Different Cultural Contexts. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 682 (1), 201
- [26] Ginszberg, E., Ginsburg, S.W., Axelrod, S., & Herma, J.L. (1951). *Occupational Choice*. New York: Columbia University.
- [27] Harold, J. (2005). Between Intrinsic and Extrinsic Value. *Journal of Social Philosophy*, 36(1), 85-106.
- [28] Hegney, D., Plank, A., & Parker, V., (2006). Extrinsic and Intrinsic Work Values: Their Impact on Job Satisfaction in Nursing. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 14 (4), 271-281.
- [29] Ho, C.C. (2006). *A Study of the Relationship between Work Values, Job Involvement, and Organizational Commitment among Taiwanese Nurses*. Unpublished Thesis. Australia: Queensland University of Technology

- [30] Hofstede, G. (1980), *Culture's Consequences: International Differences in Work-Related Values*, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [31] Hutter, W.F. (2017). Misalignment of Values can Lead to Sub-Optimal Performance. *Smart Business*. Retrieved from <https://www.sbsonline.com>
- [32] Judge, T.A. & Bretz, R.D. (1992). Effects of Values on Job Choice Decision. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 77 (3), 261-271
- [33] Jurgensen, C.E. (1978). Job Preferences (What Makes a Job Good or Bad). *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 63, 267-276.
- [34] Kaasa, A. (2011). Work values in European countries: Empirical evidence and explanations. *Review of International Comparative Management / Revista de Management Comparat International* 12 (5): 852–62.
- [35] Kahn, W. A. (1990). Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work. *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(4), 692-724. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256287>
- [36] Kahneman, D., & Deaton, A. (2010). High income improves the evaluation of life but not emotional well-being. Princeton, NJ: Center for Health and Well-being, Princeton University. Retrieved from <https://www.pnas.org>
- [37] Kalleberg, A. L. (1977). Work values and job rewards: A theory of job satisfaction. *American Sociological Review* 42 (1): 124–43.
- [38] Kazimoto, P. (2016). Employee Engagement and Organizational Performance of Retails Enterprises. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 6, 516-525. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajibm.2016.64047>
- [39] Kaygin, E. & Gulluce, A.C. (2013). The Relationship between Career Choice and Individual Values: A Case Study of a Turkish University. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3 (3).
- [40] Knoob, R. (2010). Work Values and Job satisfaction. *The Journal of Psychology*, 128(6)
- [41] Korkki, P. (2010). Job satisfaction Vs. a Big Pay Check. *The New York Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com>
- [42] Krishnan, T.N. (2012). Diversity of Career System: The Role of Employee Work Values. *The Indian Journal of Industrial relations*, 47(4), 685-699
- [43] Kuchinke, K.P., Kang, H.S. & Oh, S.Y. (2008). The Influence of Work Values on Job and Career Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment among Korean Professional Level Employees. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 9(4), 552-564. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03025670>
- [44] Kuok, A.C.H., & Taormina, R.J. (2017). Work Engagement: Evolution of the Concept and a New Inventory. *Psychological Thought*, 10 (2), 262-287.
- [45] Lebednik, C. (2017). How to Use Tangible Measurement in a Performance Review. *Management*. Retrieved from <https://bizfluent.com>
- [46] Leedy, P.D. (1974). *Practical Research: Planning and Design*. New York: Macmillan
- [47] Levinson, H. (2003). Management by Whose Objective? *Harvard Business Review*. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org>
- [48] Liao, C.W., Lu, C.Y., Huang, C.K. & Chiang, T.L. (2012). Work Values, Work Attitude, and Job Performance of Green Energy Industry Employees in Taiwan. *African Journal of Business Management*, 6 (15), 5299-5318. DOI: 10.5897/AJBM11.1449
- [49] Listau, K., et al (2017). Work Engagement: A Double-Edged Sword? A Study of the Relationship between Work Engagement and the Work-Home Interaction Using the

- ARK Research Platform. *Scandinavian Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 2(1): 4, 1–13, <https://doi.org/10.16993/sjwop.20>
- [50] Liu, K., Maoyan, S. & Wang, N. (2020). Work Values and Turnover Intention in Chinese New Generation Employees Based on Multiple Intermediaries. Paper Presented at 35th IBIMA Conference, Seville Spain.
- [51] Lofquist, F.H. & Davis, R.W. (1978). Values as Second-Order Needs in the Theory of Work Adjustment. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 12, 12-19.
- [52] Mankoff, A.W. (1974). Values-Not Attitudes-Are the Real Key to Motivation. *Management Review*, 63, 23-29.
- [53] McKay, D.S. (2018). Clarifying Your Work Values Lead to Job Satisfaction. Balance Careers. Retrieved from <https://www.thebalancecareers.com>
- [54] McLeod, S. (2019). What are Independent and Dependent Variables? Simply Psychology. Retrieved from <https://www.simplypsychology.org>
- [55] Meglino, B.M., Ravlin, E.C. & Adkins, C.L. (1989). A Work Values Approach to Corporate Culture: A Field Test of Value Congruence Process and Its Relationship to Individual Outcomes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 74(3), 424-432
- [56] Merriman, K.K. (2016). Extrinsic Work Values and Feedbacks: Contrary Effects for Performance and Well-being. *Journal of Human Relations* 70 (3).
- [57] Miller, M.F. (1974). Relationship of Vocational Maturity to Work Values. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 5(3), 367-371.
- [58] Nohari, L. (2013). Work Values and Its Relationship to Job satisfaction. Unpublished Thesis. Durban, South Africa: University of KwaZulu-Natal.
- [59] Nystrom, M. (2020). Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation for Employees. Retrieved from <https://blog.o2employmentservices.com/intrinsic-vs-extrinsic-motivation-employees>
- [60] Patro, C.S. (2013). The Impact of Employee Engagement on the Organization's Productivity. Paper Presented at 2nd International Conference on Managing Human Resources at the Workplace, December 13-14, 2013, India.
- [61] Pryce, J. (2014). Work Values: A Formidable Domain within the Context of People's Lives. *Etropic*, 13 (2)
- [62] Pryor, R. (1979). In Search of a Concept: Work Values. *The Vocational Guidance Quarterly*, 28, 250-258.
- [63] Putti J.M, Aryee S, Liang T.K. (1989). Work Values and Organizational Commitment: A Study in the Asian Context. *Human Relations*, 42(3):275-288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872678904200305>
- [64] Ravari, A., Hejazi, H.B., Ebadi, A., & Oswandi, K. (2012). Work values and job satisfaction: A qualitative study of Iranian nurses. *Nursing Ethics*, 20(4).
- [65] Robino, J.A. (2007). Aligning personal values and corporate values: A personal and strategic necessity. *Employment Relations*, 25(3), 23-35.
- [66] Rokeach, M. (1973). *The Nature of Human Values*. New York: The Free
- [67] Ronen, S. (1978). Personal values: A basis for work motivational set and work attitude. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 21(1), 80-107.
- [68] Rowley, C. & Harry, W. (2011). *Managing People Globally*. Netherlands: Chandos Publishing.
- [69] Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55, 68-78.
- [70] Singh, V. (2019). The Impact of Job Engagement and Organizational Commitment on Organizational Performance. In book: *Management Techniques for Employee*

- Engagement in Contemporary Organizations. Hershey PA, USA: IGI Global.
<https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-7799-7.ch013>
- [71] Shrestha, R. (2019). Employee Engagement and Organizational Performance of Public Enterprises in Nepal. *International Research Journal of Management Science*, 4(1).
- [72] Super, D. E. & Sverko, B., eds. (1995). *Life Roles, Values, and Careers: International Findings of the Work Importance Study*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass. Zytowski, D. G. 1994. "A Super Contribution to Vocational Theory: Work Values." *Career Development Quarterly*, 42:25-31.
- [73] Schaufeli, W. B. & Bakker, A. B. (2004). Job demands, job resources, and their relationship with burnout and engagement: A multi-sample study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25, 293–315. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.248>
- [74] Schicker, A. (2020). Extrinsic Motivation: The Downside of being A Goal Junkie. Retrieved from <https://procrastination.com>
- [75] Schwartz, S. H. (1992). Universals in the content and structure of values: Theoretical advances and empirical tests in 20 countries. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology* 25 (1): 1–65.
- [76] Somers, M. J., & Birnbaum, D. (1998). Work-related commitment and job performance: it's also the nature of the performance that counts. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 4(8), 621-634.
- [77] Schwartz, S. H. (1999). A theory of cultural values and some implications for work. *Appl. Psychol. Int. Rev.* 48, 23–47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/026999499377655>
- [78] Teng, L.C. (2010). Relationship between Work Values and Job Involvement: A Study among Manufacturing Operators in the Packaging Industries in Penang. Unpublished Thesis: Malaysia: Universiti Sains Malaysia.
- [79] Thomas, T.P. (2013). The Effect of Personal Values, Organizational Values and Person- Organization Fit On Ethical Behavior and Organizational Commitment Among Substance Abuse Counselors: A Preliminary Investigation. IOWA University: IOWA Research Online. Retrieved from <https://ir.uiowa.edu>
- [80] Tranquillo J, & Stecker M. (2016). Using intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in continuing professional education. *Surg Neurol Int.* 7(7), 197-9. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2152-7806.179231>
- [81] Tricore (2016). HR Professionals Should Pay Attention to Employee Engagement. Retrieved from <https://tricorehcm.com>
- [82] Ueda, Y. & Ohzono, Y. (2012). Effect of Work Values on Work Outcomes: Investigating Differences between Job Categories. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 3 (2).
- [83] Van-Vianen, A.E.M. & Dijk, F.V. (2007). Work value fit and turnover intention: Same-source or different-source fit. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22 (2), 188-202
- [84] Vansteenkiste, M., & De Witte, H. (2002). The Relation between Work Values, Basic Need Satisfaction, Job Satisfaction, and Well-Being: A Self-Determination Approach. Unpublished paper. Belgium: University of Leuven
- [85] Vroom, V. H. (1964). *Work and motivation*. New York: Wiley.
- [86] Warr, P. (2008). Work values: some demographic and cultural correlates. *J. Occup. Organ. Psychol.* 81, 751–775. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317907X263638>
- [87] Wilkinson, D. (2000). *The Researcher's Toolkit*. London: Springer
- [88] Wollack, S., Goodale, J.G., Wijting, J.P. & Smith, P.C. (1971). Development of the Survey of Work Values. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 55(4), 331-338.

- [89] Wu, T.S., Lee, K.C. Liu, Y.S., & Ou, H.M. (1996). Development of Work Values Inventory. Unpublished paper. Taiwan: National Chung Hsing University.
- [90] Xiao, S.F. & Froese, F.J. (2008). Work Values, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment in China. Paper Presented at the AIB Annual Conference, Milan, Italy, 2008. Retrieved from <http://aib.msu.edu/events/2008/>
- [91] Zimmerman, M.J. (2019). Intrinsic Vs. Intrinsic Value. Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy. Retrieved from <https://plato.stanford.edu>.
- [92] Zytowski, D.G. (1970). The Concept of Work Values. *The Career Development Quarterly*, 18,(3).

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